

1 [Supplementary material](#)

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3 **Higher soil moisture increases forest temperature buffering**

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6 Appendix A - Additional figures and tables

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8 Fig. S 1. Correlation between model variables for year 2018. offset = daily difference between
9 maximum temperature inside and outside the forest, Tmax_macro = daily reference maximum
10 temperature outside the forest derived from elevation-corrected weather station data, VPD = daily
11 vapour pressure deficit at the reference weather station, VWC = daily soil volumetric water content,
12 averageVWC = site-averaged soil volumetric water content, Copen = canopy openness, HeatLoad =
13 topographic heat load.

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17 *Fig. S 2. Daily soil water content (VWC) during summer (June, July, August) in four consecutive years*

18 *from day 1 (1st June) to day 92 (31st August). Each line represents one of 57 sites, coloured by the*

19 *average soil water content over one summer.*

20

21 *Fig. S 3. Daily maximum temperature offset during summer (June, July, August) in four consecutive*
 22 *years plotted over time from day 1 (1st June) to day 92 (31st August). Each line represents one of 57*
 23 *sites, coloured by the average offset over one summer.*

24

25 *Table S 1. Model summary for the generalized additive mixed model on all years' data.*

Component	Term	Estimate	Std Error	t-value	p-value	
A. parametric coefficients	(Intercept)	-1.979	0.112	-17.647	0.0000	***
Component	Term	edf	Ref. df	F-value	p-value	
B. smooth terms	te(VWC,COpen,HeatLoad)	41.730	41.730	29.906	0.0000	***
	s(VPD)	8.872	8.872	66.607	0.0000	***

Signif. codes: 0 <= '***' < 0.001 < '**' < 0.01 < '*' < 0.05

Adjusted R-squared: 0.524, Deviance explained NA

lme.REML : NA, Scale est: 0.658, N: 4968

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28 Appendix B - Single-year analyses

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30 We performed the same analysis as in the main text on each year, separately, using the same subset
31 of 23 days to reduce temporal autocorrelation and using plot ID as a random effect. Overall patterns
32 were similar to the all-year model regarding the variance explained by the models (ca. 50 %, Table S
33 2), the general cooling effect of soil moisture on forest understory temperatures (Fig. S 4). However,
34 we also found differences in the strength of these relationships, e.g. average soil moisture effects
35 were strong in 2018 and 2021 but weaker in 2019 and 2020 (Fig. S 4a). Additionally, the strength and
36 sometimes even the direction of the interaction between soil moisture and canopy openness or heat
37 load changed between years (Fig. S 4b-c, Fig. S 5).

38 In 2018 and 2021, sensitivity to soil moisture was stronger under more closed
39 canopies, a pattern that could be explained by sites with a more closed and dense canopies having a
40 higher Leaf Area Index (LAI) and thus a larger transpiring surface per hectare compared to sites with
41 more open canopies - as a consequence they can cool the understory more efficiently. Conversely, in
42 the years 2019 and 2020, we found no clear interaction and a generally weaker effect of soil
43 moisture on the offset (shallower slopes than in 2018 and 2021) under open as well as under closed
44 canopies. Maybe this was a situation, where less transpiration from trees in more open canopies was
45 compensated by increased evapotranspiration from the understory vegetation and the soil (both
46 receiving more sunlight under open canopies).

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48 *Fig. S 4. Partial response curves for soil volumetric water content (VWC) alone (a) and in interaction*

49 *with canopy openness (b) and topographic heat load (c) for the single years models (Table S 2)..*

50 *Predictors that are not explicitly displayed in a plot have been averaged for that particular plot. Years*

51 *differed in their average temperature and moisture with 2018 being the warmest and driest year and*

52 *2021 the coolest and wettest (Fig. 3). Note that the observed range of VWC is different across the*

53 *years.*

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57 2018

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2019

59 2020

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2021

61 *Fig. S 5. Partial response plots of the three-way interaction (canopy openness * soil moisture (VWC) **
 62 *heat load) for the single years models (Table S 2). Partial effect = daily maximum temperature offset,*
 63 *VWC = daily soil volumetric water content. Copen = canopy openness, panels refer to different*
 64 *topographic heat load values, as specified at the top (lower values = shaded slopes, higher values =*
 65 *sunny slopes). Plot created with the gratia package in R.*

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68 *Table S 2. Model summaries of the single year generalized additive mixed models.*

69 **2018**

Component	Term	Estimate	Std Error	t-value	p-value	
A. parametric coefficients	(Intercept)	-1.595	0.100	-15.996	0.0000	***

Component	Term	edf	Ref. df	F-value	p-value	
B. smooth terms	te(VWC,COpen,HeatLoad)	26.793	26.793	19.692	0.0000	***
	s(VPD)	8.707	8.707	45.341	0.0000	***

Signif. codes: 0 <= '****' < 0.001 < '***' < 0.01 < '**' < 0.05

Adjusted R-squared: 0.501, Deviance explained NA

lme.REML : NA, Scale est: 0.473, N: 1242

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71 **2019**

Component	Term	Estimate	Std Error	t-value	p-value	
A. parametric coefficients	(Intercept)	-1.889	0.089	-21.259	0.0000	***

Component	Term	edf	Ref. df	F-value	p-value	
B. smooth terms	te(VWC,COpen,HeatLoad)	14.850	14.850	15.238	0.0000	***
	s(VPD)	8.330	8.330	39.775	0.0000	***

Signif. codes: 0 <= '****' < 0.001 < '***' < 0.01 < '**' < 0.05

Adjusted R-squared: 0.542, Deviance explained NA

lme.REML : NA, Scale est: 0.480, N: 1242

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73 **2020**

Component	Term	Estimate	Std Error	t-value	p-value	
A. parametric coefficients	(Intercept)	-1.774	0.074	-23.874	0.0000	***

Component	Term	edf	Ref. df	F-value	p-value	
B. smooth terms	te(VWC,COpen,HeatLoad)	15.402	15.402	12.069	0.0000	***
	s(VPD)	8.715	8.715	30.238	0.0000	***

Signif. codes: 0 <= '****' < 0.001 < '***' < 0.01 < '**' < 0.05

Adjusted R-squared: 0.493, Deviance explained NA

lme.REML : NA, Scale est: 0.538, N: 1242

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2021

Component	Term	Estimate	Std Error	t-value	p-value	
A. parametric coefficients	(Intercept)	-2.658	0.084	-31.692	0.0000	***
Component	Term	edf	Ref. df	F-value	p-value	
B. smooth terms	te(VWC,COpen,HeatLoad)	8.249	8.249	34.757	0.0000	***
	s(VPD)	8.736	8.736	55.802	0.0000	***

Signif. codes: 0 <= '***' < 0.001 < '**' < 0.01 < '*' < 0.05

Adjusted R-squared: 0.491, Deviance explained NA

lme.REML : NA, Scale est: 0.645, N: 1242

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